

PID38004_AndreaMiccoli_miRBass

Version 3

Description

This DMP defines the collection, processing and publishing of datasets that will be obtained from the AquaServ transnational access project "miRBass - Transcriptome mining for non-lethal biomarkers discovery in the European seabass" (PID: 38004).

Funder

Grant

Researchers

giuseppe scapigliati (0000-0001-9730-9394), Elena Sarropoulou (0000-0003-1824-9405), Andrea Miccoli (0000-0002-4545-7229)

Organizations

Tuscia University, Institute for Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnology, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research

1. Main Info

Title of Plan: [PID38004_AndreaMiccoli_miRBass](#)

Description:

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

[Tuscia University](#)

[Institute for Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnology](#)

[Hellenic Centre for Marine Research](#)

Contact: [Miccoli Andrea \(andrea.miccoli@cnr.it\)](#), [Sarropoulou Elena \(sarris@hcmr.gr\)](#)

Access: [Public](#)

2. Ethics

Introduction:

Sample collection and processing complies with EU animal welfare regulations. Animal manipulation complies with the guidelines of the European Union Directive (2010/63/EU) and the Italian Legislative Decree 26 of March 4, 2014 "Attuazione della Direttiva 2010/63/UE sulla protezione degli animali utilizzati a fini scientifici". As the proposal aims to address knowledge gaps in understanding miRNA functions in marine teleosts by focusing on the European seabass,

a species that is frequently challenged by lethal bacterial and viral infections, the work couldn't be carried out without conducting experiments or other scientific procedures on living animals.

Descriptions

Ethics

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Template: [Horizon Europe - Ethics](#)

Type: [Ethics](#)

1 Ethics

1.1 Ethics

1.1.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No

1.1.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No

3. Dataset descriptions

Introduction:

Description of the dataset to be generated within the miRBass project

Descriptions

AQUASERV | Molecular Biology & Omics | sequencing

The datasets to be generated from the miRBass project are

- Raw and processed small RNA sequencing data (sncRNAs, including miRNAs)
- Raw and processed 3' UTR RNA sequencing data for miRNA-target interaction studies
- Gene expression profiles from head kidney and spleen tissue
- qPCR validation data

Template: [AQUASERV | Molecular Biology & Omics | sequencing](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 dataset type

1.1.1 Please specify the dataset type

RNA sequencing (sncRNAs and 3' UTR) qPCR data

2 Your research data

2.1 Sequencing machine details

2.1.1 Sequencing chemistry / kits used

Sequencing machine: Nextseq 2000 NEB small RNA library kit and Lexogen 3'UTR library preparation

2.2 General type of data

2.2.1 additional information about your dataset

Transcriptomics

2.3 Type of data (format)

2.3.1 Data format

fastq data (data volume is expected in the range of tens to hundreds of GB)

2.4 Documentation and data quality

2.4.1 How will the data be documented and described/analysed? Please specify which type of documentation record are you planning to use (e.g. paper or electronic labbook, online resource) and which software are you planning to analyse your data with

Data will be documented electronically and analyzed within the RStudio environment.

2.5 Storage and Backup

2.5.1 Do you use any intermediate storage devices? Please describe your backup plan.

SSD drive and HCMR server.

2.6 Accessibility and long-term storage

2.6.1 Long term data storage - database

NCBI SRA database.

2.6.2 Accession number

The BioProject ID will be communicated via email once the first SRA submission is completed.

2.7 Your metadata

2.7.1 Metadata format

Excel spreadsheet.

2.7.2 How is your metadata connected to the research data

A metadata table will be produced to unequivocally describe samples once they will be statistically analyzed for differential expression.

2.7.3 Metadata storage

SSD drive, HCMR server and NCBI SRA portal

3 Licence/embargo

3.1 Licence

3.1.1 Under what license will you publish your research data?

CC BY

3.2 Embargo on data release

3.2.1 Embargo details

Dataset will become publicly accessible or searchable within the NCBI portal at a specific date or upon publication, whatever occurs first.

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